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FIELD TESTING AND DEMONSTRATION OF A SMART GRID READY CHARGING PARK

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of the research project "controlled charging cells", which was conducted in the period from 10/2019 to 06/2021 and funded by the Ministry of the Environment of the State of Baden-Württemberg. During the project, a public charging park was set up in a municipal parking garage consisting of 16 charging points. This demonstration test facility was integrated into the operating concept for charging infrastructure of the municipal utility. The goal was to create a blueprint for the intelligent grid connection of parking garages, (company) parking lots and underground garages (PPT) and thus to develop the basis for a safe as well as cost-efficient grid integration of the e-charging infrastructure into the distribution grid and also to demonstrate it in a field test. Through the collaboration of the municipal utility, the local distribution grid operator and the Ulm University of Applied Science (THU), a safe intervention option for specifying the maximum possible charging power was implemented and demonstrated. A smart meter infrastructure-based solution was used, as it allows secure communication of a control command and is also well suited for further rollout thanks to a high degree of automated and standardized processes. For all components, developed or used, attention was paid to the use of e-mobility and energy network standards (OCPP, IEC 61850) so that the solutions developed can be used independently of individual manufacturers and are transferable nationally and internationally. While ready-to-use solutions are already available for all individual problems, integration into an overall system that is usable and tested for municipal services that operates PPT and distribution grid operators is currently still missing.

INTRODUCTION

Problematically high energy consumption peaks due to the charging infrastructure for e-vehicles occur in particular when many charging columns are installed in a confined space [1]. This is especially the case in parking garages on a large scale. How these charging stations are frequented has not yet been conclusively clarified and also depends to a large extent on the surrounding area. Parking garages in city centers, for example, are very busy during the opening hours of the surrounding stores, but can also be relatively underutilized for longer periods outside business hours. On the other hand, company parking lots are very busy during the day on weekdays, but are often virtually unused on weekends and overnight. These examples illustrate the range of factors that need to be taken into account when planning and implementing a charging park. In addition, the grid connection of the e-charging park and also upstream grid resources can be overloaded if the simultaneity factor is high. This can be countered by expanding the network capacity, but high network expansion costs are to be expected. The replacement of network equipment (transformers, cables) is seen as a classic network expansion measure. Alternatively, intelligent control of the charging stations can ensure that the power consumption does not exceed the maximum capacity of the infrastructure. In the best case, this succeeds without noticeable restrictions in the use of the e-charging infrastructure. The state of the art here is local charging management, which distributes the maximum available power to the active charging points. If demand exceeds the set limit, the power at individual (or all) charging points is reduced according to a defined distribution scheme. In this process, additionally recorded user information is also particularly helpful, covering, for example, the planned duration of use of the charging point

or the amount of energy to be charged. Communication between the charging point and the user/vehicle is still inadequate in this context, although Plug & Charge (ISO 15118) is a possible solution [2]. The cumulative effect of several charging parks, which are operated in the same segment of an electricity distribution network, is hardly taken into account in current planning. Although statistical methods can often prove that the probability of an overload is extremely low, this worst-case scenario cannot be completely ruled out. Therefore, the establishment of a possibility for external power reduction by the responsible network operator is currently a major topic in the discussion about concrete measures for the expansion of the e-charging infrastructure.

SMART GRIDS AND SMART METER INFRASTRUCTURE

The expansion of renewable energies and their high level of acceptance among the population, local authorities and many companies is already posing challenges for many power grids. The starting point for this development in Germany is the smart meter infrastructure based on smart meter gateways and controllable local systems (CLS) introduced by the Act on the Digitization of the Energy Transition [3]. The smart meter infrastructure is composed of a digital electricity meter and a so-called smart meter gateway, a communication unit. Smart meters enable consumers and companies to better and more conveniently manage their electricity consumption or the feed-in of their electricity, for example from solar cells on the roof or e-charging columns, and to benefit from new tariffs. The security aspect, both in the system (energy supply) and for the required ICT (information and communication technology) of the smart grid components, plays a decisive role in the success of the energy transition.

Fig. 1 System Architecture using the German Smart Meter Infrastructure - control of the charging park using the Smart Meter Infrastructure CLS channel (purple)

DISTRIBUTION NETWORK OPERATION

Decentralized energy systems have so far been integrated into an energy system that is organized top-down. Under the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG), special roles were created for local energy systems and the direct use of this energy, up to and including the solar tax on the local

use of energy. An important component for the flexible use of the energy to be distributed locally is, among other things, the charging infrastructure for electric vehicles. A future distributed energy system embedded in a smart grid offers completely new possibilities - both for operational grid operation and for energy trading and billing models. However, in order to operate its grid safely and efficiently in the event of a high penetration of e-charging infrastructure, the grid operator needs comprehensive knowledge of the state of the power grid upstream of the charging park. In addition, he needs the ability to make a decision on power reduction at short notice, for which the network status calculation in low temporal resolution (less than 15 min) is a prerequisite. The current state of the art here is a design calculation of the power grid for new construction or conversion work, which takes into account statistical specifications for the expected power and energy flows. The possibility of controlling a charging park can be implemented in Germany via the Energy Industry Act §14a, but is difficult to apply in practice due to the lack of grid status determination at the distribution grid level [4].

SOLUTION CONCEPT

As a framework condition, the number of 16 charging points with a charging power of 22 kW each was specified. For the entire charging park, 100 kW maximum total power is reserved at the connection point of the underground car park at the associated transformer. A local load management system is used for power distribution, which dynamically distributes the available total power to the individual charging processes according to a pre-selected algorithm and without further external intervention. In practice, this means that from the 5th charging process, which charges at full capacity ($5 \times 22 \text{ kW} = 110 \text{ kW}$), the load management intervenes and reduces the power according to the selected distribution algorithm at the individual charging points.

The objective was to ensure the smoothest possible use of the charging park by visitors to the parking garage, while keeping the costs per charging point as low as possible. In addition, an optimized use of installation space and materials was already aimed for during the planning phase. The result of the planning was a solution combining 4 wallboxes with a capacity of 22 kW and 6 with $2 \times 11 \text{ kW}$ (max 22 kW). These double wallboxes distribute the available power to the two built-in charging points, with single occupancy 22 kW are also available there. The purpose here was to create an opportunity to investigate the extent to which these different wallbox types can cover the different user profiles.

The connection of such an energy system to the network control center of a distribution network operator is critical to safety. The main challenge here is the provision and configuration of the various system instances involved (smart meter gateway admin, CLS management backend, experimental distribution network control center), so that the connection of e-charging infrastructure using the

encrypted CLS channel of the intelligent metering system (iMSys) could be investigated and tested [5].

In addition to the secure communication link via the smart meter infrastructure, the connection of the systems within the property must be ensured. In the project, a Restful API of the central master unit of the charging park was used as an interface to the local charging management.

Furthermore, a real-time simulation environment [source] developed at THU is used. This was developed with the goal of evaluating the feasibility of real-time state estimation in existing low-voltage feeders of the test areas, as grid cells, based on iMSys and CLS infrastructure. The simulated grid cells and the predefined metering points were modelled in the distribution grid simulation environment within the distribution grid automation agent. Based on the calculated grid state, the distribution grid automation agent sends a grid congestion measure to the grid control room when needed. The devices in the field receive the request as control commands from the network control room of the THU when the occurring congestion situations need to be eliminated. The network control room communicates these control commands as well as the measurement data to the CLS gateways in the field via the IEC 61850 protocol.

IMPLEMENTATION

An essential part of the project was the procurement and installation of the charging infrastructure. Extensive planning and preparatory work had to be carried out by the municipal utility.

For the substructure, a curtain-type supporting structure including an installation road was produced. A T-shaped facing with an air space behind it was used. In addition, there is a load-bearing hollow profile along the entire length of the charging park, which can accommodate the power cables as well as the communication cables.

For the electrical installation, existing cable routes could be used for the most part, but suitable solutions had to be found at neuralgic points such as cable routes that were too narrow or fire compartment passages.

The distribution network operator installed a measuring device on the associated local network transformer, which can record both the power at the grid connection point of the parking garage and the overall utilization of the transformer.

For integration into the existing parking guidance system/charging guidance system of the municipality, LoRaWan parking sensors, user information displays and the connection to the higher-level systems for authentication and billing of charging processes were implemented.

Fig. 2 Overview of the 16 charging points installed in the demonstrator, implemented using 6 twin wall boxes and 4 single wall boxes (picture ©Ulmer Parkbetriebs-GmbH)

Furthermore, a floor coating in green with a black border was implemented, which at the same time delimits the parking space as such, but also refers to the e-charging infrastructure. A photorealistic pattern in leaf optics was chosen as the graphic design in the form of a foil for the curtained installation level, which is intended to visualize the contribution of e-mobility to the reduction of CO₂ emissions. This design is also to be used for the charging stations to be built in the future in order to create a recognition effect among users.

Parameterization of local controllers and setup of interfaces

When it comes to power distribution within the charging park, there is a wide range of options for implementation. Simultaneous charging of many electric vehicles in a parking garage or parking lot leads to various challenges. This is mainly due to the limited power availability, which is limited by the limited capacity of the existing lines and transformers. In addition, each vehicle has different charging requirements due to the different parking time, battery charge level, and driving distance after parking. To this end, THU has developed a simulation model of the charging infrastructure for electric mobility. The focus was on the simulation of a charging park controller (LPR), which controls the interaction of several charging columns and the interaction with the network. In the process, the interfaces to the outside of the grid as well as to the inside of the individual charging stations were also addressed. One step in the implementation of a LPR, is the definition of the interface between the charging station and the charging station controller and between the charging station controller and the control unit. In order to find the right communication model for the interface between the LPR and the CLS gateway, criteria have been developed that should be met. The interface should be as standardized as possible, take into account the specifications for integration in the THU Smart Grid Lab, use open communication interfaces for networked mobility services and offer the possibility of real-time communication [6].

Control of the e-charging park

To implement the desired functionality, an adaptation of the software on the CLS component was carried out. The software serves as a protocol converter between the local instance in the field and the experimental distribution network control center at THU. The distribution network control center uses IEC61850 for the telecontrol connection. In the meantime, the IEC61850 is also used for the connection of decentralized components in the low voltage [7]. Thus, the software was adapted to address the Restful API of the master unit of the charging park in order to communicate the regulation command. Furthermore, the software on the CLS gateway was extended to include the ability to read measured values from the separately installed measuring device. The software combines this information and makes it available to the control system via IEC61850 communication.

The system design and development of the IT systems at THU includes in particular an experimental distribution network control center, the smart meter gateway admin and the EMT platform as SaaS as well as the CLS backend. In addition, proprietary tools are used to support parameterization of the CLS components and device management, tools for parameterization of the control system (automated creation of configuration and data model), test systems for function verification as part of a pre-deployment test, and a cross-system tool for monitoring and alerting. For the implementation of business and application logics, the system landscape was supplemented by a state estimator for distribution networks and a logic module for bottleneck elimination, including a mockup for development support [8].

CONDUCT OF THE PILOT TEST

The pilot test at the campus of the THU consists of two logical charging parks, each with a wallbox and a charging management system. In addition, a three-phase external socket was installed in order to be able to flexibly test the products of other manufacturers.

The integration of the charging stations as well as the charging management system was carried out with the help of an open-source OCPP server [9] [10]. This software is published as open source and is operated on a locally installed embedded computer. This component is used for the initial configuration and authentication of the charging station users. To test the load limitation, a special interface of the charging management system was used, which works according to the Restful principle.

In this case, the measurement and control is acquired by a CLS gateway and connected to the experimental distribution network control room of the university via iMsys and secured channel. The software of the CLS gateway was extended for this purpose in order to be able to send the command used for load limitation. The measuring device can also be read out by the software running on the CLS gateway.

Fig. 3 Extension of the Smart Grid Laboratory by two separately controllable wallboxes, each of which is configured as a charging park with an associated master unit

FIELD TESTING

The solution previously designed and already tested in the pilot test is used for the loading park demonstrator. Adjustments were still necessary due to a different firmware status of the devices used. In addition, the CLS application was extended to support the Janitza-UMG801 measuring device used on site. In order to test the connection of the measuring device in advance, a corresponding test setup was set up in the smart grid laboratory. The effort for on-site integration of the CLS gateway in the demonstrator could thus be limited to two dates. As already tested in the pilot test, the demonstrator also uses an SMGW with a mobile radio connection for the communication link. The connection proved to be stable in this application, even in practical use. On a positive note, the solution now in use automatically re-establishes the data connection after brief interruptions.

Fig. 4 Visualization of the charging park control by THU network control system (controlled limitation of the charging park power in green; actually used charging power in orange)

RESULTS

The demonstrator charging park and its upstream distribution network were incorporated as a permanent test facility in cooperation with the network operator. Solutions for network status recording were developed in order to gain experience for the controlled charging of e-mobiles in PPT. This enables, for example, the implementation of dynamic load management in the parking garage based on the network condition of the upstream local network. The evaluation of parking, user and charging behaviour as well as customer feedback regarding the controlled charging of e-mobiles has also started. This evaluation will be continued in order to be prepared in particular for the increasing spread of e-vehicles. Particular attention was paid to developing a standardized list of requirements for local load management and interfaces to upstream control levels. Furthermore, the focus was on establishing a scalable charging solution with load management for both long-term and short-term parkers in a parking garage of the municipal parking garage operator together with the local energy supplier in the parking garage. This includes in particular the demonstration of a secure control via the German smart meter infrastructure by distribution network operators or market participants. For this purpose, it will be shown how a maximum retrievable value for the charging infrastructure can be specified and the ongoing charging processes regulated by means of a secure communication gateway.

OUTLOOK

Currently, the implementation effort for creating the distribution grid simulation of a cell is still high due to the complexity of the system design and the lack of metering points in low-voltage grids. This complexity is mainly due to the synchronization of multiple systems and data objects on the grid control room and in the distribution grid automation agent. However, these use cases will become more and more important for future scenarios with a very high share of distributed generators and will therefore be further investigated and optimized. In the future, the developed grid simulation in combination with the determined communication approaches should lead to an increase in the reliability of the grid state determination with simultaneous optimization of the grid operation and will be further evaluated.

The results of the work carried out will be used by municipal services in the construction of the further charging infrastructure. In a recently built parking garage, 30 charging points will be created with a reserve for expansion to 100 charging points. Furthermore, the other central public parking garages will then be successively retrofitted with charging parks; here, a size of 20 charging points will be implemented in the first expansion stage. In addition, the results will also be available to the private housing sector and companies. Here, there is still a need

for adaptation to the developed blueprint, as user behaviour and the technical boundary conditions differ. There is still a need for further research, particularly in the development of operating strategies for a charging park as part of a local energy management system, especially if other energy technology components such as battery storage or flexible consumption facilities such as industrial plants are to be taken into account in the control system.

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